

THE SPECIFIC FEATURES IN ABDULRAZAK GURNAH’S LITERARY STYLE

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Annotation. This article analyzes a somewhat nuanced aspect of the book “Paradise” by Abdulrazak Gurnah. The topic of ambivalent identities during colonial times is the focus of this article. In light of prize discussions, this article offers specific information on Gurnah’s shortlisted book Paradise. It also includes original material on the novel's structure.

Key words: *colonialism, postcolonial studies, Eurocentrism, and binaristic perspectives, ambivalent identities.*

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Abdulrazzak Gurnahning "Jannat" kitobining biroz nozik jihati tahlil qilinadi. Mustamlaka davridagi noaniq identifikatsiyalar mavzusi ushbu maqolaning diqqat markazidir. Mukofot muhokamalaridan kelib chiqqan holda, ushbu maqola Gurnahning qisqa ro'yxatga kiritilgan "Jannat" kitobi haqida aniq ma'lumotlarni taqdim etadi. Unda roman tuzilishiga oid original materiallar ham mavjud.

Kalit so'zlar: *mustamlakachilik, mustamlakachilikdan keyingi tadqiqotlar, yevrosentrizm va binaristik nuqtai nazarlar, ambivalent o'ziga xosliklar.*

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется несколько нюансированный аспект книги Абдулразака Гурны «Рай». Тема амбивалентных идентичностей в колониальные времена находится в центре внимания данной статьи. В свете обсуждений призов в этой статье представлена конкретная информация о книге Гурны «Рай», вошедшей в шорт-лист. Он также включает оригинальный материал о структуре романа.

Ключевые слова: *колониализм, постколониальные исследования, европоцентризм и бинаристские взгляды, амбивалентные идентичности.*

Abdulrazak Gurnah is a Tanzanian author who lives in the UK, aside from being an author, he is also an academic. He works at the University of Kent. He has previously worked at other universities including ones in Tanzania. He has a focus on postcolonial writing and writings from he like edits essay collections of writings by African authors and things like that. He was one of the authors that was interviewed at one point, we thought. He was going to be interviewed a few more times. We think, he sounds like an interesting writer. He talked about sort of stumbling into writing and how his writing really started on him coming to England and as a way of interpreting the feeling of having left

home and the situation that he was in terms of having left that homeland behind and that kind of feeling of having left home and moved to a different place and finding you finding your bearings again.

It is definitely something that comes in quite a lot in “Paradise” which is one of his best-known books and the reason that we analyzed because it seems to be pretty highly regarded [1]. We suppose in terms of his work. So, we thought it sounded, he sounded like of all of the authors were interviewed for the first week of that course. We thought he sounded like the most interesting. His book sounded like the ones that were most appealing to us. We suppose and he is one of the ones that we had not heard of before. So, hence we looked into him and we ended up ordering this one online course.

Paradise was written in 1994 and it was shortlisted for the Booker prize and the Whitbread prize in that year. We think it was definitely a deserved to get on the shortlist and we do not know what did win that year, but we feel like shortlist is the right level for this book. It was the most amazing book. We have ever read but it was definitely a really good quality book and with a really solid foundation to it, if that makes sense. It has set around the turn of the 20th century in the years leading up to World War [2]. That has obviously never explicitly stated in the book, because they do not know that it is the years leading up to World War. But that was the sort of time period that it was based in and it was set in initially in a small town in Tanzania. But then the main character Yusuf travels quite a bit and the story follow him as he moves from place to place and as he grows in age. So, we would basically describe this as a coming-of-age novel. In our previous articles, we wrote it is coming of age novel with kind of a symbolism and reminiscences. We suppose of something like Dante’s “Inferno” [3], where it is definitely not that level but as you can tell from the title and there is definitely like ideas that are drawn on in relation to ideas of heaven and hell. We suppose and definitely religion.

This book described as a kind of response to Conrad’s “Heart of darkness”. We think that is strictly true, but definitely we think it plays into the idea of postcolonial writing and like being a response to maybe some of the existing narratives. In particular it subverts the narrative that Europeans were the first people and the only people who were interested in exploring deep into the Heart of Africa and that Europeans [4] were the only ones, who had trading systems in place who had any kind of legal system or anything and it definitely also subverts the idea of Africa as being one kind of homogenous mass prior to the establishment of colonial rule, that is definitely something that really hangs over this book is kind of the specter of colonialism. It goes from use of mentioning the first few white people. He sees to it being constantly have you heard about the English and the Germans and such like this increasing kind of sense of threat. From the increasing grip of colonialism on the area that they are working in that they are living in terms of that coming-of-age novel. Because we think that is the most important part of this book.

It is very much a character-driven book. We would say as opposed to a plot-driven book. The plot is interesting but quite gentle it is kind of it goes on a journey, but it does not go on a journey, if that makes sense, but it is enjoyable in that way in terms of this

coming-of-age aspect. We would say that Gurnah is really effective at capturing Yusuf as a young boy and when he was sort of 10 or 11 and we had just like a really brilliant vision of him in our head at that age. and we think he gets slightly weaker as Yusuf gets older there are moments in his adolescence that are really convincingly captured and really well drawn and but there are other patches, where it does not either he feels like he is still a bit younger or he kind of does not feel like. He has enough of a presence in the book almost. We did enjoy the journey that he went on. We would say there was a lot of this sense of threat, that we were talking about some of it is related to colonialism [5], some of it is about Yusuf as a person and there is a lot about how he looks he is supposed to be a really good-looking young man.

There is a sense of threat that was built up around that to us was never fully paid off. We could see where the payoff was almost supposed to be but we felt that it was perhaps slightly lacking from the tension that had been kind of indicated if that makes sense, but we did enjoy it and we think the real beauty of this book is the writing style, the themes that it brings in. we think this book is a good book, if you are an attentive reader and if you are really good at or if you really enjoy picking up on symbolism. It makes sense, there is basically the characters in the book are kind of in a way divided into people, who travel and people who do not travel and the people who travel, tell stories that are then relayed through people who travel and do not travel in a kind of like a story web, if that makes sense and some of them are these kinds of scary stories of the wolf men and you know they did. you know that the Germans can. we do not know like something like burn your skin just by touching it or something like that and like these miraculous powers that they are supposed to have and some of them are like beautiful stories of did you know in India.

There is this paradise garden and things like that and we think at first. We were just reading those for interest, but then we are kind of later realized we should have been paying more attention because a lot of the things that come up in the stories are symbols that you are kind of supposed to remember and then they kind of come up not necessarily in physically embodied. But those ideas of those symbols are brought up again later in the book. We would say pay more attention than we did if you are going to read this book and we think this is one book that would benefit from having an introduction.

After you have read the book or you know for some from some notes and things as well, but maybe that is just us. We like a classic book with notes and to us this felt more like a classic book that should have had notes than it did like the typical contemporary book. We would read we did enjoy it weirdly. we would say we wanted to enjoy this book more than we did and we expected to enjoy this book more than we did if we were going to do a star rating, we would say we really thought it was going to be five stars and we were really hoping to make it five stars and we are kind of almost maybe gave it a little bit more leeway.

In our mind like we were trying to push it up to that fifth star but it has more four stars just because of the character not being fully realized like the sense of threat. that we

mentioned not quite paying off and us as an inattentive reader you know reading this on our break on night shifts you know not exactly bringing our best mind to it and maybe not getting all of the references and all of the picture that he was building entirely. The other thing we wanted to say was that and he portrays this. We were going to say world but region we suppose starting in Tanzania but moving further into the interior of Africa and that is an area with a clash of religions and races not like leaving aside colonialism, but even within the groups that were there already and because of that we think he was trying to do it honestly.

There is racist language, there is sometimes homophobic language, there is definite certain treatments of people with physical disabilities or scarring and things like that and we think he is doing it because he wants to portray that society as honestly as he thinks that society would have been, but just to be aware of that if you are going to be reading it the thing that bothered us. Maybe slightly more was that all of the female characters in this book are there exclusively based on how they interact with Yusuf and they are just there to interact with Yusuf in given ways that generally relate to relationships, if that makes sense in a way. we did not mind it because it is a book very definitely about Yusuf and about him growing up and about him starting to have those experiences of having first relationships. But in another way, its kind of would have been nice, if some of them had some personality other than whether or not they found him if that makes sense and some of them are definitely some of the characters overall male or female are caricature as much as they are characters.

It has got some interesting things to say as well we think about servitude and slavery and dignity and control and there several of the characters in this book are what are called “Rouhani”, people who have been basically given to this merchant character as payment of a debt, so effectively they are slaves but it looks at for instance, people reasons why people might stay even when their slavery period has ended and that definitely comes up and like what it means to be free.

As a conclude, we suppose and what it means to be like going back to this idea of paradise and symbolism there is lots and lots of garden symbolism and nature symbolism in this book and it is set up that paradise is the garden and but what if you had that paradise what could be going on in paradise to not make it a paradise and obviously being trapped there would be a thing that would make it turn it from being a paradise into being a form of hell. All of that is discussed in a really honest way and written style some of the sentences are just really lovely. We think we would definitely recommend this book.

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